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QR Determinants of Tourists' Adoption of QR Code Payment Systems in Bangladesh: Extending the UTAUT2 Framework

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Abstract

The tourism industry has been experiencing the dynamic technological innovations and these innovations are greatly influencing tourist behavior and decision-making process. Bangladesh has significant potential to promote sustainable tourism through technological orientation. However, despite recent progress in digital payments, tourists' adoption of QR code payment systems in Bangladesh remains limited. Therefore, this study explores the determinants of QR code payment adoption in Bangladesh with a particular focus on the tourism sector. Grounded in a modified UTAUT2 framework, this study examines how technological, behavioral and risk-related factors influence the tourists' intentions to use QR code payments during travel. A quantitative research

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design was employed and 704 responses were collected via an online survey. Data were analyzed using the structural equation modeling (SEM) through SmartPLS (version 3.2.9) and SPSS (Version 27). The results indicate that performance expectancy (PE), attitude (ATD), facilitating conditions (FC) and perceived risk (PCR) significantly influence tourists' behavioral intention (BVI). In contrast, effort expectancy (EE), habit (HBT) and perceived trust (PCT) do not. This study enriches the existing body of the literature on technology adoption in tourism. Therefore, the findings offer practical implications for managers while suggesting potential avenues for future research.

Keywords: *QR code, QR payment, Digital payment, Technology adoption, Tourism technology, UTAUT2*

Paper type: Research paper

1. Introduction

The tourism industry in Bangladesh has experienced remarkable growth in recent years, driven by the country's rich natural and ecological resources. Studies highlight Bangladesh's strong tourism potential across multiple dimensions, including cultural heritage, coastal tourism, and eco-based destinations (Roy et al., 2020; Uchinlayen et al., 2022). Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation (BPC) states that the tourism sector is set to expand at an average of about 7.5 percent per annum, with Cox's Bazar alone earning 15 million USD in 2020 despite the global COVID-19 slowdown (Islam, 2024). Also, international visitor spending has been increasing, while domestic tourism expenditure has also demonstrated continual growth (Bangladesh Monitor, 2024). However, transactions in Bangladesh have largely relied on the traditional cash-based payments. While cash transactions remain widely accepted and suitable for face-to-face transactions, there are issues with security, physical handling requirements and inefficiencies associated with foreign currency exchange (Kocher, 2024; Mandhare et al., 2024). In contrast, contactless payment solutions offer greater convenience and safety, particularly in tourism. Therefore, digital and contactless payment systems have been identified as an emerging trend that can act as an alternative to overcome the issues faced by the tourism and hospitality industry.

Prior studies indicate that contactless hospitality services can enhance customer satisfaction and trust, even among users with relatively low levels of technological readiness (Hao & Chon, 2021). Empirical evidence further suggests that contactless payments are perceived as user-friendly, reliable, and time-saving, thereby increasing consumers' willingness to adopt them (Park et al., 2022). During the COVID-19 pandemic, mobile banking demonstrated a significant

alternative solution to reduce physical contact and ensure continuity of transactions (Salam et al., 2021). The socio-economic and digital culture of Bangladesh further supports the diffusion of digital payment technologies. The total number of mobile internet users in Bangladesh is around 115.27 million and a total of around 187 million (As of November 2025) cellular mobile connections were active (AMTOB, 2025). Moreover, the increasing trend towards contactless payment systems can be supported by the changing digital environment and initiatives towards digitalization in Bangladesh.

Digital payment initiatives such as mobile financial services and the Bangla QR aim to enhance the financial inclusion across urban and rural areas, with the target of 75% of retail transactions to be conducted digitally by 2027 (The Daily Star, 2023). Nevertheless, beyond improving the transaction efficiency and accessibility, quick response (QR) code payments are increasingly aligned with green FinTech objectives supporting sustainability-oriented financial innovation (Rayun et al., 2025). Contemporary technologies, including AI, machine learning (Shahriare Satu et al., 2023), and Blockchain (Azad et al., 2022) have been dynamically changing the business environment. These technological innovations are influencing consumers behavior and attitudes and affecting on their decision making process (Salam et al., 2024, 2026). Therefore, the existing body of literature explores the diverse aspects of the use, engagement and adoption of technologies. However, despite the technological advancements and digital environment, the adoption of payment innovations, such as those based on QR codes, needs more academic investigation within sector-specific contexts.

lthough QR codes have been increasingly adopted in Bangladesh's tourism sector, dedicated academic studies specifically examining their adoption, consumer perceptions, or risk and trust perspective on the tourism and hospitality sector in Bangladesh remain limited and largely emerging. Thus, this study aims to investigate the key determinants influencing the adoption of QR code payment systems in the tourism and hospitality industry in Bangladesh, using a modified version of the UTAUT2 model.

2. Literature Review

The quick response (QR) code and near-field communication (NFC) payment options are both classified as self-service technologies (SST), which allow customers to conduct transactions using their mobile devices (Chamika Hewawasam, 2024). A QR code is a matrix code that can be read

using specialized scanners or the great-resolution cameras found on smartphones and can hold many types of data (Susanto et al., 2022). QR codes provide numerous benefits, including large data storage capacity, rapid recognition, readability from all angles, and error correction, as well as multiple versions (Tiwari, 2016). Almeida et al. (2019) noted that future studies on NFC, QR codes, and mobile wallets would be particularly useful, as the perceptions of visitors regarding these technologies depend on their age and travel experience, which are relevant for tourism management. Prior studies suggest that digital payment solutions can enhance service efficiency and customer convenience (Lai & Liew, 2021; PH, 2023), which are particularly important in tourism, where transactions are frequent (Shrestha et al., 2025). One of the main reasons for the low adoption of QR code payments is the lack of knowledge and awareness among both consumers and merchants (Mishra et al., 2024).

Mobile payment systems are influencing the financial transactions, but regulatory fragmentation, cybersecurity vulnerabilities and privacy concerns hinder universal adoption (Mada, 2025). Suebtimrat & Vonguai (2021) demonstrates that attitude is a statistically significant indicator of consumer intention to use QR payment. Regarding mobile wallets, Chawla & Joshi (2019) discovered that attitude greatly affects intention. Ashrafi & Easmin (2023) noted a significant finding by integrating prospect theory and perceived value theory and showed that attitude does not influence behavioral intention. Perceived value and trust were discovered to have a positive effect on QR code payments (Ashrafi & Easmin, 2023). Musyaffi et al. (2021) employed the UTAUT model in their research and revealed that trust, performance expectancy, and perceived security are critical factors in QR code adoption. Despite the growing body of empirical evidence on the multiple antecedents of QR code and mobile payment adoption, the extant research findings are fragmented and theoretically inconsistent.

Using the extended TAM model, Türker et al. (2022) investigated user acceptance of QR code and uncovered that perceived trust was the most critical factor, followed by perceived security, perceived compatibility, and perceived usefulness. Srivastava et al. (2021) showed that factors such as effort expectancy, trust, and three other factors have a major impact on the behavioral intention (Srivastava et al., 2021). Similarly, grounded on UTAUT, Gupta & Arora (2020) supported that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, habit, and facilitating conditions are significant predictors of behavioral intention. Huang (2023) found that utilitarianism, anxiety, trust, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, and

habit have a direct impact on older adults' preference to participate in mobile shopping. These empirical inconsistencies highlight the need to use robust technology acceptance frameworks to explain technology adoption behavior.

Nevertheless, the increasing dependence on smartphones and the internet, low digital literacy and poor connectivity limit the use of contactless payment systems (S. Hussain et al., 2025). However, findings related to other determinants remain theoretically inconsistent. In contrast, other research finds attitude to be statistically insignificant (Kamal et al., 2023; Syaputra et al., 2025), implying that payment adoption may be driven more by functional value than by evaluative beliefs. Similarly, trust has been identified as both a critical enabler and an insignificant factor in different empirical settings, possibly due to users' growing familiarity with multiple payment platforms and the ease of switching between them (Shuhada Sehat et al., 2024). Effort expectancy and habit also demonstrate mixed effects (Esawe, 2022; Rayun et al., 2025; Suo et al., 2021), with some studies identifying them as significant predictors of intention (M. Hussain et al., 2019; Rayun et al., 2025), while others report negligible influence, particularly among technologically experienced users.

To explain adoption behavior, scholars have extensively applied technology acceptance frameworks such as the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT), its extension UTAUT2, the technology acceptance model (TAM), and the theory of reasoned action (TRA). Empirical findings across these models consistently identify performance expectancy and facilitating conditions as important predictors of behavioral intention toward QR code and mobile payment systems. These constructs capture users' perceptions of usefulness and the availability of necessary resources, which are particularly relevant in digital transaction environments.

3. Research framework and hypothesis development

UTAUT framework integrates several adoption theoretical insights and explains technology acceptance behavior. With an enhancement and extension of the theory of reasoned action (TRA), UTAUT is used to explain users' intentions to use information technology, as well as actual usage behavior (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The UTAUT2 model is an extension of the UTAUT model and can be applied to investigate the adoption of technology on a wider spectrum of users, thus giving a more holistic view of behavioral intention (Ain et al., 2016; Chang et al., 2019; Foroughi et al., 2023). Behavioral intention refers to the deliberate decision or willingness to engage in a specific

behavior resulting from conscious thought processes (Davis, 1989). According to Ajzen (1985), an individual's level of motivation and resolve to make an effort to carry out a specific action is called their intention.

The key determinants of UTAUT are performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The updated framework incorporates these primary predictors from UTAUT, and introduces three additional factors (Zhao & Bacao, 2020). This model's hypothetical correlations have been empirically validated and endorsed by multiple studies in the acceptance of online tickets (Rodríguez & Trujillo, 2014), mobile payment among tourists (Wu et al., 2021), online hotel booking (Chang et al., 2019), digital wallet (Elasaria & Nurabiah, 2024), and mobile health (Zhu et al., 2023). Grounded on the UTAUT2 model, this study specifically focuses on key determinants that are expected to have an impact on behavioral intention with regard to the adoption of QR code payments in the context of tourism and hospitality.

3.1 Performance expectancy (PE)

Performance expectancy (PE) is the extent to which an user believes that using a digital payment system will improve the performance (Musyaffi et al., 2021). In the context of the study, the performance expectancy means that the users cognitively evaluate that the monetary transaction will improve the efficiency, convenience, and effectiveness of the transaction, which will improve the performance and well-being (Sehat et al., 2024). According to prior research, Performance expectancy strongly impacts behavioral intention, such as the implementation of QR code payment (Suebtimrat & Vonguai, 2021), virtual tourism (Bilynets et al., 2023), and financial technology (Shaikh & Amin, 2023). In the tourism context, where both time and convenience are valued because many transactions in the tourism industry are usually opportunistic, it indicates that tourists will readily embrace QR code payment platforms as long as they feel that these platforms enhance efficiency and quality of payment. This leads to the following hypothesis:

H1. PE has a positive and significant effect on tourists' BVI to use QR code payment systems.

3.2 Effort expectancy (EE)

The concept of effort expectancy (EE) refers to the level of effort required to use QR codes for digital transactions (Musyaffi et al., 2021). Davis (1989) proposed that the intention of an individual to adopt a new system could be predicted based on the perceived usefulness of the system and the degree of effort required to use the system. Effort expectancy is a factor that influences the execution of the cashless method in the behavioral intention (Agarwal, 2020). Studies have demonstrated that EE substantially impacts behavioral intention. Specifically, the adoption of QR code payment applications (Sehat et al., 2024), mobile payment (Salam et al., 2023), internet banking (AbuShanab & Pearson, 2007) and learning analytics (El Alfy & Kehal, 2024). The more positive tourists' perceptions of the overall QR code payment process are, the more likely they are to use these systems. Hence, this study proposed the following hypothesis:

H2. EE has a positive and significant effect on tourists' BVI to use QR code payment systems.

3.3 Facilitating conditions (FC)

Facilitating conditions (FC) are the extent to which an individual perceives that the technology has the resources and infrastructural support that are needed to be effective. The UTAUT framework argued that the external environment can either facilitate or hamper the adoption and utilization of technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The effect of enabling conditions on behavior intentions has been demonstrated in various aspects, including adoption of m-banking (Zhou et al., 2010), metaverse adoption in tourism (Calderón-Fajardo et al., 2024), green FinTech (R.-R. Lin & Lee, 2024), and online banking (I. Khan et al., 2017). Due to potential regional differences in infrastructure quality and service availability, FC takes on greater meaning in the context of tourism, particularly in emerging economies (Ali et al., 2025). Thus, tourists are more likely to adopt a QR code-based payment system if they perceive that the necessary technical and institutional support is readily available. Hence, this study proposed the following hypothesis:

H3. FC has a positive and significant effect on tourists' BVI to use QR code payment systems.

3.4 Habit (HBT)

Habit (HBT) refers to the extent to which the use of a particular technology has turned out to be automatic due to previous repeated behaviors or experiences. A stronger habit is developed in

relation to the frequency of using technology. A feeling of addiction to utilizing technology is another common manifestation of this (Aisyah et al., 2023). The impact of habit on the intention to use technology has been studied in various contexts, including online banking (I. Khan et al., 2017), adoption of mobile health (Duarte & Pinho, 2019) and mobile payment (K.-Y. Lin et al., 2018). Regarding this study context, it is expected that the travelers' habits influence their behavioral intentions to use QR code payment systems. Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4. HBT has a positive and significant effect on tourists' BVI to use QR code payment systems.

3.5 Perceived risk (PCR)

Perceived risk (PCR) is an important determinant for the adoption and acceptance of internet-based payment transactions (Slade et al., 2013). PCR describes how seriously people take the possibility of experiencing the risk, whether they be monetary, social, psychological, physical or time-related (Zhang et al., 2012). Studies indicate that perceived risks associated with an application can negatively affect the user experience and impede its adoption (Chen, 2008). As per the results of a prior study, PCR has a substantial influence on the intention to adopt technology. Studies have explored multidimensional aspects, including mobile payment (Abrahão et al., 2016), cashless payment (Namahoot & Jantasri, 2023) and m-commerce (Zhang et al., 2012). Tourists who perceive higher risks associated with QR code payment systems will likely have lower willingness to adopt these technologies. Hence, this study posits that:

H5. PCR has a significant effect on tourists' BVI to use QR code payment systems.

3.6 Perceived trust (PCT)

Perceived trust (PCT) is a key determinant of technology adoption (Singh & Sinha, 2019). Perceived trust becomes crucial in a virtual context due to the increased degree of transaction uncertainty compared to a traditional one (Roca et al., 2009). Prior studies have shown that trust influence behavioral intentions in contexts such as m-commerce (Abdallah et al., 2020), mobile payments (Salam et al., 2023), and online pharmacies (Saraswat & Singh, 2025). Since tourists are likely to deal with unfamiliar merchants and payment systems during their travel, their trust perceptions can significantly affect their intention to use QR code payment systems. By evaluating this, the following hypothesis has been proposed:

H6. PCT has a positive and significant effect on tourists' BVI to use QR code payment systems.

3.7 Attitude (ATD)

Attitude (ATD) is a significant component in determining behavior (Chiu et al., 2017). In the theory of planned behavior (TPB), attitude is described as a person's general evaluation of conducting a specific behavior, indicating the extent to which they hold the behavior positively or negatively (Ajzen, 1991). In this study, attitude refers to tourists' overall positive or negative evaluation of QR code payments, including interest, perceived favorability, and need for information. Prior studies have demonstrated that attitude significantly influences the behavioral intention, including digital marketing in the tourism sector (Ahmad & Rasheed, 2025), AI adoption (Emon & Khan, 2025), metaverse adoption in hospitality (Chakraborty et al., 2025), and adoption of smart technologies in tourism (Bano & Siddiqui, 2024). Similarly, Suebtimrat & Vonguai (2021) noted that attitude significantly impacts the behavioral intention toward QR code payment. Therefore, the attitude of tourists is likely to be an important factor that influences their intention to use QR code payment systems. Consequently, this study hypothesized the following:

H7. ATD significantly impacts the BVI of using QR code payment in tourism.

Hence, Figure 1 represents the proposed research model.

Figure 1. Proposed research model

Source(s): Authors' own creation

4. Methodology

4.1 Data collection

This study employed a quantitative research design, using survey instruments. The questionnaire's design incorporates a Likert scale consisting of five response options, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). All the measurement items have been adapted from the prior literature. Appendix A1 contains all of the measuring items for each construct. After the initial development of the questionnaire, it was given to three PhD students and a faculty member to check the clarity and validity. Based on their recommendations, some minor wording changes have been made and were distributed online through different social media platforms. This study didn't include any clinical trials. However, to adhere to the ethical principles, respondents were assured of the data security and privacy. The participation in the survey was entirely voluntary and informed consent was obtained. A set of inclusion and exclusion criteria was set for selecting the engaged data. Respondents were eligible to be included in the study, as demonstrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Participant inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
(1) Traveled within Bangladesh	(1) Never used QR code payments
(2) Must have experience using a QR code payment system on their travels	(2) Given incomplete surveys
(3) Completed the questionnaire fully with appropriate responses	(3) Filled logically inconsistent or unrelated responses, such as choosing the same scale point for all questions (e.g., choosing "strongly disagree" for every question)

Source(s): Table by authors

4.2 Sampling technique and size

In this study, a non-probability purposive sampling method was used. Researchers employed this sampling strategy to ensure that the study's participants shared the relevant demographic information. Purposive sampling was used to intentionally recruit respondents with the same relevant characteristics needed for the study (Campbell et al., 2020). Such an approach enabled researchers to reach individuals who may be able to shed light on the parameters that influence the adoption of QR code payments. However, in PLS-SEM, a common rule-of-thumb is that the sample size should be at least 10 times the largest number of indicators for any single construct or the largest number of structural paths pointing to a latent variable (Barclay et al., 1995; Hair et al.,

2017). In addition, it was proposed that for more complex models, larger sample sizes may be necessary, such as 200-300 or more (Hair et al., 2010). Therefore, a total of 704 responses have been obtained, and 661 were found valid based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, which meets the minimum sample size required.

4.2 Data analysis technique

This study investigated the conceptual model using partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). SPSS 27 and Smart PLS 3.2.9 have been used for the data analysis. For SEM, the analysis is typically conducted in two main stages: assessment of the measurement model and assessment of the structural model (Hair et al., 2017). Knowledge of the respondents' demographic profile is useful for interpreting the results of the PLS-SEM and for judging the representativeness of the sample. However, understanding the demographic profile of respondents is important for interpreting the PLS-SEM results and assessing the representativeness of the sample.

5. Results

5.1 Demography of respondents

Table 2 offers an analysis of the survey participants, categorizing them based on their gender, age, level of education, and preferred payment methods. The data reveal a sample size of 661 participants, with a higher percentage of females (58.9%) than of males (41.1%). Most of the respondents were in the 21-30 age group (86.2%), while a few were less than 20 and above 30. In terms of digital payment methods, most of the participants used BKash (70.3%) and Nagad (22.1%), while a few used Rocket and other methods. Overall, the study participants were mostly in the 21-30 age group and familiar with digital payment systems, which made the study suitable for assessing the use of QR code in the context of tourism.

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Demographic	Characteristics	N	%
Gender	Male	272	41.1
	Female	389	58.9
Age	Under 20	48	7.3

	21-30	570	86.2
	31-40	27	4.1
	41-50	13	2.0
	More than 50	3	0.5
Preferred Payment Apps	Nagad	146	22.1
	BKash	465	70.3
	Rocket	37	5.6
	Others	13	2.0

N = Number of the respondents, % = Relevant percentage

Source(s): Table by authors

5.2 Results of analysis

To confirm the factorability, this study conducted the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) tests (Bartlett, 1951; Kaiser, 1970). The results in Table 3 indicate that the KMO value is 0.860, which exceeds the recommended threshold of 0.60. This indicates that the data are highly suitable for factor analysis. In addition, the results of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity are statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 6916.632$, $df = 276$, $p < 0.001$), which rejects the null hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix. The results support the fact that the variables are correlated and appropriate for further multivariate analysis such as exploratory factor analysis and the development of PLS-SEM models.

Table 3. KMO and Bartlett's test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.860
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6916.632
	Df	276
	Sig.	0.000

Source(s): Table by authors

This study also utilizes Harman's single-factor test to identify the common method bias (CMB). The test is based on concepts from Harman's texts on factor analysis (Harman, 1976). The common method bias variance test yielded a result of 18.108% in Table 4. This indicates that it satisfies the criteria being less than the 50% threshold set by Harman's single test (Rodríguez-Ardura & Meseguer-Artola, 2020).

Table 4. Results of Harman's single-factor test for common method Bias

Factor	Total Variance explained					
	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.125	21.353	21.353	4.346	18.108	18.108

Source(s): Table by authors

Table 5 shows that each indication on the outer loading (λ) exceeds the validity test's threshold of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2011), with ATD1 loading 0.665. The loading value greater than 0.60 is still acceptable for an empirical study (Purwanto & Sudargini, 2021). The average variance extracted (AVE) values are above the threshold of 0.5 (Hamid et al., 2017). This ensured that the convergent validity has been established. Henceforth, the Cronbach's Alpha (α) and composite reliability (CR) of all variables exceed the threshold value of 0.7 (Hair et al., 2017) except the α value of attitude (ATD).

Table 5. Convergent validity and internal consistency reliability of the measurement model

Constructs	Indicators	Convergent validity		Internal Consistency Reliability	
		Λ	AVE	CR	α
Behavioral	BVI1	0.844			
Intention	BVI2	0.819	0.683	0.866	0.768
	BVI3	0.815			
Performance expectancy	PE1	0.791	0.631	0.837	0.708
	PE2	0.833			
	PE3	0.758			
Effort expectancy	EE1	0.894	0.737	0.893	0.832
	EE2	0.922			
	EE3	0.751			
Facilitating Condition	FC1	0.756	0.645	0.845	0.726
	FC2	0.822			
	FC3	0.829			
Habit	HBT1	0.822	0.787	0.917	0.872
	HBT2	0.925			
	HBT3	0.911			
Perceived	PCR1	0.879	0.805	0.925	0.881

Risk	PCR2	0.899			
	PCR3	0.912			
Perceived	PCT1	0.942			
	PCT2	0.827	0.748	0.899	0.854
Trust	PCT3	0.821			
	ATD1	0.665			
Attitude	ATD2	0.773	0.577	0.802	0.642
	ATD3	0.832			

λ = Factor loadings; AVE = Average variance extracted; CR = Composite reliability; α = Cronbach's alpha

Source(s): Table by authors

Although the alpha value for ATD ($\alpha = 0.642$) is slightly lower than the traditional 0.70 cutoff, it is considered acceptable for exploratory research and PLS-SEM analysis when the composite reliability and AVE satisfy the criteria. Overall, the results support the adequacy of the measurement model for subsequent structural model analysis.

The discriminant validity has been established through the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio (Table 6). HTMT values are generally below the recommended threshold of 0.85 (Kline, 2023). Even though a strong relationship is observed between the constructs of HBT and PCT, with a value of 0.850, this is still within the accepted threshold. In addition, strong relationships, such as those between PE and FC (0.740), ATD and BVI (0.742), and PE and ATD (0.658), are theoretically justifiable in the context of technology adoption, while at the same time satisfying the discriminant validity criteria.

Table 6. Heterotrait–Monotrait (HTMT) ratios assessing discriminant validity among constructs

	ATD	BVI	EE	FC	HBT	PCR	PCT	PE
ATD								
BVI	0.742							
EE	0.095	0.095						
FC	0.710	0.667	0.053					
HBT	0.104	0.084	0.434	0.074				
PCR	0.052	0.083	0.028	0.056	0.026			
PCT	0.082	0.048	0.414	0.058	0.850	0.037		
PE	0.658	0.644	0.069	0.740	0.099	0.032	0.111	

PE = Performance expectancy, EE= Effort expectancy, FC = Facilitating condition, HB = Habit, PCR = Perceived risk, PCT = Perceived trust, ATD = Attitude, BVI = Behavioral intention

Source(s): Table by authors

The variance inflation factor (VIF) is a widely used diagnostic measure for detecting the multicollinearity. As shown in Table 7, the outer VIF values for all measurement items range from 1.221 to 2.828. Also, all the inner VIF values range from 1.164 to 2.102, which are well below the commonly recommended threshold of 5 (Hair, 2009; X. Li et al., 2023). This suggests that the measurement model is free from multicollinearity issues.

Table 7. Variance inflation factor (VIF) values assessing multicollinearity among measurement items

Indicators	VIF	Indicators	VIF
ATD1	1.221	HBT1	2.152
ATD2	1.332	HBT2	2.474
ATD3	1.251	HBT3	2.383
BVI1	1.594	PCR1	2.51
BVI2	1.558	PCR2	2.828
BVI3	1.544	PCR3	2.22
EE1	2.045	PCT1	2.017
EE2	2.177	PCT2	2.484
EE3	1.707	PCT3	2.041
FC1	1.382	PE1	1.415
FC2	1.494	PE2	1.471
FC3	1.427	PE3	1.306

PE = Performance expectancy, EE= Effort expectancy, FC = Facilitating condition, HB = Habit, PCR = Perceived risk, PCT = Perceived trust, ATD = Attitude, BVI = Behavioral intention

Source(s): Table by authors

5.3 Hypothesis Testing

Once the measurement model's reliability and validity have been established, the proposed structural model was tested. Based on the recommended statistically significant levels, a significant relationship was defined when the corresponding *t*-value was more than 1.64 at the 95% confidence level (Hair et al., 2019). The path coefficients with the corresponding *t*-statistics and level of significance of all the hypotheses are demonstrated in Table 8.

The results showed a strong positive effect of PE on BVI, as demonstrated by hypothesis H1 ($\beta = 0.201, t = 4.893, p < 0.001$). indicating that perceived functional benefits can stimulate tourists to use QR code payments. Hypothesis H2 was rejected, indicating that EE does not have a significant effect on BVI ($\beta = -0.046, t = 1.346, p > 0.05$). Hypothesis H3 represents that FC has a considerable and favorable influence on BVI ($\beta = 0.228, t = 5.566, p < 0.001$). This suggests that tourists are more likely to adopt QR code payment systems when they perceive adequate technical, infrastructural and institutional support to be available. Hypothesis H4 was rejected, indicating HBT does not significantly influence BVI ($\beta = -0.028, t = 0.610, p > 0.05$). This suggests that the tourists' intentions to use QR code payments are not driven by habitual behavior. Hypothesis H5 shows that PCR has a positive impact on behavioral intention ($\beta = 0.065, t = 2.103, p = 0.036$). This suggests that when tourists perceive QR code payment systems as credible and trustworthy, they are more likely to intend to use them. Hypothesis H6 was also rejected ($\beta = 0.050, t = 0.960, p > 0.05$), indicating that PCT doesn't have an effect on BVI. Finally, hypothesis H7 demonstrated that ATD has a strong significant influence on BVI ($\beta = 0.340, t = 8.384, p < 0.001$). This indicates that the tourists with more favorable attitudes toward QR code payment systems are substantially more likely to intend to use them.

Table 8. Hypothesis testing results

Hypothesis	Path	β	\bar{x}	<i>sd</i>	<i>t</i> -statistics	<i>p</i> - values	Remarks
H1	PE → BVI	0.201	0.201	0.041	4.893	0.000	<i>Accepted</i>
H2	EE → BVI	-0.046	-0.052	0.034	1.346	0.179	<i>Rejected</i>
H3	FC → BVI	0.228	0.23	0.041	5.566	0.000	<i>Accepted</i>
H4	HBT → BVI	-0.028	-0.027	0.045	0.610	0.542	<i>Rejected</i>
H5	PCR → BVI	0.065	0.067	0.031	2.103	0.036	<i>Accepted</i>
H6	PCT → BVI	0.050	0.046	0.052	0.960	0.337	<i>Rejected</i>
H7	ATD → BVI	0.340	0.337	0.041	8.384	0.000	<i>Accepted</i>

β = Path coefficient; \bar{x} = Sample mean; *sd* = Standard deviation

PE = Performance expectancy, EE= Effort expectancy, FC = Facilitating condition, HB = Habit, PCR = Perceived risk, PCT = Perceived trust, ATD = Attitude, BVI = Behavioral intention

Source(s): Table by authors

6. Discussion

This study examined the key determinants influencing the adoption of QR code payment systems with a particular focus on the tourism and hospitality industry in Bangladesh. The results offer significant theoretical and practical implications regarding tourists' adoption behavior in the context of a developing country experiencing rapid growth in digital payments and mobile connectivity. However, consistent with the UTAUT2 model, performance expectancy (PE) emerged as a significant predictor of behavioral intention. This suggests that tourists would be more motivated to use QR code payments if they perceive functional benefits in terms of efficiency and convenience. This result is consistent with previous studies emphasizing the importance of performance expectancy in driving adoption behavior, particularly in the context of mobile payments (Salam et al., 2023), cashless tourism (Rayun et al., 2025), and AI acceptance in tourism (Topsakal & Çuhadar, 2025).

In contrast, effort expectancy (EE) was not statistically significant, indicating that the ease of use is no longer a factor in the adoption behavior of tourists, particularly from a QR code payment system perspective. This is possibly because mobile payment systems are common and well-known. This is aligned with the prior studies of AI adoption in tourism (Topsakal & Çuhadar, 2025) and service robot adoption in tourism (B. Lin & Lee, 2025). Moreover, habit (HBT) was not statistically significant in terms of behavioral intention, indicating that the adoption behavior is episodic in the context of tourism and not habitual in the context of QR code payments. These findings are supported by the previous findings on cashless tourism (Rayun, et al., 2025), adoption of ChatGPT in tourism (Foroughi et al., 2025).

The facilitating conditions (FC) were a strong and positive predictor of behavioral intention. This reinforces the significance of perceived technical, infrastructural and institutional support. It is apparent from the results that tourists are likely to adopt the technology if they perceive adequate resources, internet connectivity and support from service providers. These findings are aligned with the prior studies on tourism app adoption (Ramli et al., 2024) and mobile application usage (Medeiros et al., 2022). Regarding risk and trust, perceived risk (PCR) was found to have a small positive effect on behavioral intention. This suggests that although security and privacy issues are important factors in the adoption decisions of tourists, they are not the dominant factors in their decisions. This is supported by prior studies on the adoption of autonomous vehicles (Kenesei et al., 2025) and the adoption of AI in designing (Y. Li et al., 2025). On the other hand,

perceived trust (PCT) was found to be non-significant. This suggests that tourists' trust in the use of the QR code platform is high enough due to their prior exposure to mobile payment services such as BKash and Nagad. This study adds to the literature regarding the role of risk and trust in the adoption of technology in the tourism industry.

Notably, attitude (ATD) was revealed to be the strongest predictor of behavioral intention. This suggests that tourists who have a positive attitude towards QR code payment are much more likely to use the technology. This finding highlights the significance of attitude constructs in the TPB and the TAM, which support that the adoption of technology is significantly influenced by individuals' positive perceptions, interest, and willingness to seek more information about the technology. This finding aligns with the prior studies on cloud-based collaborative platform adoption (Feng & Haridas, 2025), adoption of ChatGPT in education (Alqaisi et al., 2025), adoption of unified payment interface (Razi-ur-Rahim et al., 2024), and the adoption of gamified website (Hsu, 2024).

Therefore, the results suggest that in the context of Bangladeshi tourism, the main factors influencing the adoption of QR code payments are functional benefits, facilitating conditions, and attitude, while ease of use, habit, and trust are less important. Theoretically, this study extends UTAUT2 by empirically supporting the generalizability of the model in a tourism setting in a developing country and by highlighting the relative importance of attitude and functional factors.

6.1 Theoretical contribution

This study contributes to the existing body of literature on technology adoption by extending UTAUT2 to the tourism industry in emerging economies, which has numerous significant theoretical implications. While UTAUT2 has been widely applied in retail and general consumer payment contexts, its applicability to tourism-specific QR payment behavior remains emerging. By focusing on tourists' behavioral intention to adopt QR code payment systems in Bangladesh, this study broadens the theoretical scope of UTAUT2. It also demonstrates how its explanatory mechanisms operate in a travel-related, situational usage context. The empirical findings refine UTAUT2 by identifying a distinct pattern of construct relevance in tourism settings. Specifically, performance expectancy, facilitating conditions, attitude, and perceived risk were found to significantly influence behavioral intention, indicating that tourists' adoption decisions are formed

by perceived functional benefits, infrastructural readiness, affective evaluations, and risk considerations associated with temporary and context-dependent transactions.

In contrast, effort expectancy, habit, and perceived trust were not significant, suggesting that ease of use, routine usage patterns, and institutional trust may play a limited role when users are non-habitual, short-term visitors rather than regular system users. This divergence from prior UTAUT2-based findings in retail and mobile payment studies contributes to theoretical refinement by highlighting context-dependent variability in adoption determinants. Furthermore, the significance of perceived risk highlights emerging theoretical concerns related to digital security and technological misuse, including risks associated with QR code fraud. This finding extends technology adoption theory by emphasizing the growing relevance of risk perceptions in the digital payment ecosystems. These insights enhance the contextual sensitivity, cross-cultural applicability, and theoretical evolution of UTAUT2 in tourism and digital payment research. Finally, by emphasizing the pre-adoption intention stage, the study advances theoretical understanding of early-stage technology acceptance in tourism, where initial willingness is critical for diffusion.

6.2 Managerial implications

The results of the study provide significant implications for implementing a QR code payment system in the Bangladeshi tourism industry. Performance expectancy, which reflects the perceived benefits of QR payments, emerged as a crucial factor driving adoption. Tourism operators can also highlight the convenience and swiftness of QR transactions, thus attracting tech-savvy tourists. Facilitating conditions is also highly significant, such as infrastructure availability and devices. For it to happen, operators need to invest in technology that reinforces smooth transactions for tourists and vendors. They can also create a seamless networking channel for QR code transactions. Further, vendors should be trained on the advantages of QR payments such that their attitude towards QR payments will improve and their resistance will mitigate.

The technology providers need to emphasize on the security features such as encryption and fraud protection, alongside creating a user-friendly system which needs to be easily accessible and include supported languages for tourists hailing from across the world. To promote the adoption of QR payments, financial institutions must enable visitors and local vendors alike with incentives suited to their needs. In addition, this digital payment initiative reflects the

environmental sustainability trend around the world by reducing paper transactions, and thus it will help towards making Bangladesh an environmentally friendly modern destination. Collaboration between these stakeholders will lead to the mass adoption of QR payments, improving the tourism experience and eventually resulting in the expansion of the sector.

6.3 Conclusion and future directions

Digital technology is increasingly integrated into the tourism industry and represents the dynamic business model to create and offer tourist-friendly experiences. This study expands on mobile-based payment innovations integrated with QR code systems in Bangladesh's tourism sector. QR code payments are less about ease of transaction and more about inclusion and modernization. This study reveals actionable insights for stakeholders by understanding how behavioral, infrastructural, and perceptual factors shape adoption. The results indicate that digital financial instruments can benefit not only tourists but also small tourism enterprises, enabling access to cashless ecosystems. Adopting safe and easy digital payment systems can not only help in global competition but also contribute to economic growth and sustainability initiatives.

However, this study holds some potential limitations. This is a cross-sectional survey-based study. Hence, future research should consider adopting a longitudinal approach to examine how tourists' attitudes and behaviors toward QR code payments evolve over time, especially post-adoption. This study is based on a quantitative survey only. Future research can benefit from qualitative methods, including interviews or focus groups, which would provide richer insight into user experience, challenges, and preferences. Likewise, the expansion of the study to other parts of regions or comparisons of multiple countries would enable cross-cultural analysis on the adoption of digital payments in tourism. Furthermore, this study is focused on the tourist perspective only. Future studies might examine the views of tourism vendors and service providers to provide a more holistic ecosystem perspective.

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Appendix

A1. Measurement of Constructs

Construct	Measure	Source
Performance Expectancy (PE)	<p>PE1: QR payments help me in travel.</p> <p>PE2: Using QR code payments in travel enables me to do tasks faster.</p> <p>PE3: Using QR code payment for travel boosts my efficiency.</p>	(Rafferty & Fajar, 2022; Venkatesh et al., 2003)
Effort Expectancy (EE)	<p>EE1: For me, learning how to apply QR code payment in travel is simple.</p> <p>EE2: QR code payments in travel seem simple to me.</p> <p>EE3: I find it simple to get good at using QR code payment in travel.</p>	(Rafferty & Fajar, 2022; Srivastava et al., 2021; Venkatesh et al., 2003)

Facilitating Conditions (FC)	<i>FC1</i> : I have resources I need to make QR code payments for travel. <i>FC2</i> : I know enough to make advantage of QR codes in travel. <i>FC3</i> : When I have problems with QR code payment in travel, I can ask others for assistance.	(Hossain et al., 2017; Venkatesh et al., 2003)
Habit (HBT)	<i>HBT1</i> : For me, using QR codes for payments in travel has grown second nature. <i>HBT2</i> : Using QR code payments in tourism makes me addicted. <i>HBT3</i> : I have to pay with QR codes in travel.	(Venkatesh et al., 2012; Zhong & Moon, 2022)
Perceived Risk (PR)	<i>PR1</i> : Using QR codes for tourism payments wouldn't make me feel safe. <i>PR2</i> : Future QR code payment systems in tourism may expose personal data to unauthorized access. <i>PR3</i> : The QR code payment mechanism in tourism is prone to errors.	(Khan & Abideen, 2023; Sawang et al., 2023)
Perceived Trust (PT)	<i>PT1</i> : In the realm of tourism, the QR code payment system is trusted. <i>PT2</i> : Honestly, I consider QR code payment systems to be a viable option for tourism. <i>PT3</i> : When it comes to tourism, I believe the QR code payment system is responsible.	(Rafferty & Fajar, 2022; Salam et al., 2023)
Attitude (AT)	<i>AT1</i> : I have an interest in QR code payment in tourism. <i>AT2</i> : QR code payment is favorable to me in tourism. <i>AT3</i> : More information about QR code payments for tourist attractions would be great.	(Jung et al., 2020)
Behavior Intention (BI)	<i>BI1</i> : In the future, I plan to make more purchases using QR codes for mobile payments. <i>BI2</i> : As soon as the chance presents itself, I will implement QR code mobile payment. <i>BI3</i> : I am interested in utilizing QR code mobile payment as an alternative to conventional payment methods for purchasing.	(Eren, 2024; Srivastava et al., 2021; Venkatesh et al., 2012)